

THE ACTIVITY OF BANKS IN TURKISTAN REGION AT THE LAST OF THE XIX AND AT THE BEGINNING OF THE XX CENTURIES

Botirov Sh.A.

Master's degree of the Faculty of History of UzNU

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7539586>

Annotation: The opening of banks in the Turkistan region by the Russian Empire, and its impact on the economic life of the country, as well as the activities of the banking departments that operating in the Russian Empire in Turkistan have been suspended in this article.

Key words: Russian Empire, Turkistan region, bank, ruble, credit, K.K. Palen.

In the second half of the 19th century, one of the main goals of introducing of colonial regimes in the Turkestan territory by the Russian empire was aimed at economic issues. The Turkestan country was transformed into a colonial territory, because of becoming a raw material base for the light industry of the developing Russian empire, and the government of the Empire was gradually seeking to restore its economy and receive great benefits from this. As the colonial administration, pursuing the interests of Russian trade-industrialists, developed a program of introduction of Russian-Asian trade, then the financial capital into Turkistan in favorable conditions.

K.K.Palen, who inspected economic and political interests of Russia in Turkestan from 1908 to 1909, described the situation as follows: "Even if the political reasons for the occupation of Turkestan are not taken into account, the country has been of interest to Russia from the very first days of its occupation by the Empire. These were, firstly, as a source of government revenue and a new market for domestic production with financially and politically, and secondly, from a colonial point of view, it was considered a new territory for the resettlement of the surplus population in the central provinces" [1, B. 229].

Banks played a key role in establishing colonial economic regimes and financial relations in Turkestan. The opening of banking institutions in the country was interests of Russia. For this purpose, King Alexander II authorized the opening of a branch of the State Bank in Turkestan on December 23, in 1874. At the time of its establishment, the bank had a fund of 4.1 thousand rubles, and mainly on the basis of promissory notes sent from Moscow and other major cities [2, B. 62]. On May 10, in 1875, a branch of the State Bank began its work in Tashkent. The management of the State Bank could not dare to register the promissory notes and issue loans (interest-bearing loans) at the expense of the product to the newly established department because the conditions of local trade and industry in the country were unknown to the bank's management. Only after a year, the

bank was opened, the Ministry of Finance allowed financial transactions to be carried out on the account of promissory notes. The Tashkent branch of the State Bank served the entire Turkestan region until the 1990s. Banks were opened in Samarkand in 1890, in Kokand in 1893, in Bukhara in 1894, in Ashgabat in 1895, and in Andijan in 1910. By the beginning of the 20th century, there were 7 branches of the State Bank of Russia in Turkestan. In 1875, promissory notes were registered with the State Bank in Turkestan amounted to 46.1 thousand rubles on January 1, in 1876, and had reached to 1.6 million rubles by 1895 [3, B. 40]. Also, as of January 1, in 1876, the daily turnover of the regional branches of the State Bank amounted to 4.1 thousand rubles on promissory notes, and by 1907 the figure was 5 million rubles. Remittances rose from 29.8 thousand rubles to 339.11 thousand rubles [4, B. 222]. The largest cash transactions were made in the Kokand branch, amounting to 19,908,000 rubles. After the Kokand and Tashkent branches of the State Bank, 3,779,000 rubles in the Samarkand branch, 3,458,000 rubles in the Bukhara branch, 3,222,000 rubles in the Ashgabat branch and 1,436,000 rubles in the Andijan branch were transferred. The state-owned bank served more traders and industrialists. Its divisions accounted for 8% of all financial transactions [5, B. 229].

The state-owned bank acted as a strict intermediary bank under its charter, operating on the basis of accounting (or circulation) of more promissory notes. The bank served the interests of Russian trading capital and met Turkestan's demand for intermediary loans in the money market. From the very first years of its existence, the State Bank emerged as a servant of all-Russian commercial capital. The state-owned bank served a larger number of merchants. In the late 19th and early 20th centuries, the state-owned bank began to lose its monopoly position in the money market of Turkestan. This process intensified, especially on the eve of the First World War and during the years of direct war.

Almost simultaneously with the state-owned bank, intermediary banks also began operating. In 1880, the “Глинка Янчевиский и К” banking house was established in Turkestan, and in 1881, the Central Asian Bank was established. It was the first joint-stock commercial bank in Turkestan in 1881 [6, B. 60]. At the same time, in 1890, one of the largest intermediary banks in the country was opened a branch of the Volga-Komsk Bank [7, B. 222]. In 1891, the branches of the Moscow International Trade and in 1893, the branches of the Volga-Kama joint-stock commercial banks of St. Petersburg were opened. Later, the Moscow Account, Merchant banks of St. Petersburg- Azov Don, Siberian and other banks

began to operate. For example, according to the charter of the Central Asian Joint-Stock Commercial Bank, the following operations were allowed: 1) registration of Russian and foreign trade bills; 2) loans and credits up to 9 months; 3) Receipt of payments on promissory notes and other interest securities; 4) Sale and purchase of government interest-bearing securities, shares, stocks and bonds through third parties; 5) Private and commercial houses consisted of the sale of goods. The bank was closed in 1911, due to its inability to increase its capital [8, B. 42].

In addition to these banks, the Russian-Chinese Bank, the Tashkent branch of the Asian-Don Intermediary Bank and mutual credit societies operated in Tashkent. In 1914, the total number of intermediary bank branches reached 40. Although banks operated in various fields in Turkestan, their main focus was on cotton operations. After all, as a result of the policy of cotton growing since the 1980s, Turkestan became the main supplier of cotton to the Russian light industry in the early 20th century.

Fergana region of Turkestan region was the leader in cotton growing. If in 1889, 49,098 hectare were planted with cotton in 9 places, by 1910 this amount was 446,116 hectare. By 1913, the cotton area had reached 300,000 acres. That is why the bank's branches were located mainly in Fergana region. In general, intermediary bank branches were located throughout Turkestan as follows: 8 in Kokand, 7 in Samarkand and Bukhara. By 1910, there were 20 branches of private joint-stock banks in Fergana region. The report of the Governor-General of the Fergana region stated that only in 1910, 7 intermediary bank branches were opened in Kokand and Andijan. [9, B. 124] Intermediary banks relied on the state bank in their operations in Turkestan. The State Bank opened 5.2% loans for intermediary banks and firms, which were distributed to intermediaries at the rate of 8-9%. For farmers, these loans were split from 40 to 50%, i.e.: as high by 5-7 times [10, B. 52].

As a result of economic reforms in the empire in the early twentieth century, the number of branches of joint-stock commercial banks in Turkestan began to increase. Between 1900 and 1909, three banks of St. Petersburg (one branch of the Volga-Kama Bank, the Bank of Siberia and the Bank of Moscow) opened branches in Central Asia. Previously, in Turkestan there were only branches of the Moscow International Trade Bank and the Volga-Kama Bank of St. Petersburg, and then by 1909, the number of branches of five banks (including the International Bank of Moscow) had risen to seven. Until 1910, the Russo-

Chinese, then the Russian-Asian Joint-Stock Commercial Bank, opened 12 branches in the country. [11, B. 40].

If we look at the activities of some banks in Turkestan, the Bank of Moscow, the Russian-Chinese Bank, the Moscow Merchant Bank, the Siberian Bank, the Russian Foreign Trade Bank and a number of other banks carried out financial transactions on promissory notes and loans.

The Russian-Chinese Bank was established in 1903. By 1910, it merged with the Northern Bank then formed the Russo-Asian Bank, and becoming the largest bank in Turkestan. The bank's credit turnover in Fergana and Tashkent amounted to 700-800 million rubles [12, B. 124]. During its existence, the Bank could take control of the largest Vadeev trade and industrial partnership in Turkestan. The strongest rivals of the Russian-Asian Bank in the country were the Moscow Commercial Bank and the Moscow Accounts Bank. The Bank of Moscow had six of its seven branches in Turkestan. In 1911, the Siberian Commercial Bank was established in Turkestan. In a short time it opened its branches in the largest shopping centers of the country in Fergana, Syrdarya regions and the Emirate of Bukhara. At the same time, the Azov-Don Bank was launched. It settled mainly in Tashkent and provided loans to intermediaries. In 1898, Don Yerbank, Poltava Yer Bank and Nizhny Novgorod-Samara Bank operated in Turkestan. The main activity of these banks was to provide loans and support to Russian immigrants. In 1903, the Poltava Land Bank appealed to the Governor-General of Turkestan to allow loans to be secured by real estate in Turkestan. His request was granted by the Russian Finance Ministry. From July 1, 1910 to 1911, the Bank issued 53 land loans for 355 thousand rubles and 181 city loans for 10144900 rubles [13, B. 228].

In short, the Russian Empire brought the financial system to Turkestan through the establishment of branches of major banks and joint-stock credit societies. Its main goal was to completely subjugate the country's economy to the metropolis. Turkestan's state-owned banking and commercial banks primarily served the interests of Russian traders and industrialists, and made a significant contribution to turning the country into a metropolitan raw material base. As a result, banking activities in the country expanded, albeit in different ways.

References:

1. Ўзбекистоннинг янги тарихи. Туркистон Чор Россияси мустамлакачилиги даврида. –Т.: Шарқ, 2000. –Б. 229.

2. Тухтабеков К.А. Чор Россиясининг Биринчи жаҳон уруши йилларида Туркистон ўлкасида ўтказган иқтисодий сиёсатининг мустамлакачилик моҳияти. т.ф.н. дисс.. –Т.: 2011. –Б. 62.
3. Носыров О.Н. XIX асрнинг охири XX аср бошларида Туркистонда акциядорлик жамиятлари ва ширкатлар тарихи. т.ф.н. дисс... –Т.: 2009. –Б. 40.
4. Юлдашев А.М. Аграрные отношения в Туркестане. – Ташкент: Узбекистан, 1969. –С. 222.
5. Там же... –С. 224.
6. Ҳаёт ва қонун. № 6, 2006. –Б. 60.
7. Деева В. и другие. Формирование рабочего класса в дореволюционном Узбекистане. –Т.: 1979. –С. 222.
8. Носыров О.Н. XIX асрнинг охири XX аср бошларида Туркистонда акциядорлик жамиятлари ва ширкатлар тарихи. т.ф.н. дисс... –Т.: 2009. –Б. 42.
9. Деева В. и другие. Формирование рабочего класса в дореволюционном Узбекистане. –Т.: 1979. –С. 124.
10. Авезова Х.Ш. XIX аср охири - XX аср бошларида Туркистонда банк ва фирмаларнинг ривожланиши. т.ф.н. дисс... –Т.: 1997. – 52 б.
11. Носыров О.Н. XIX асрнинг охири XX аср бошларида Туркистонда акциядорлик жамиятлари ва ширкатлар тарихи. т.ф.н. илмий даражасини олиш учун ёзилган дисс... –Т.: 2009. –Б. 40.
12. Деева В. Формирование рабочего класса в дореволюционном Узбекистане. –Т.: 1979. –С. 124.
13. Юлдашев А. Аграрные отношения в Туркестане. –Т.: 1968. –С. 228.
14. Усмонов, М.Т. (2021). Вычисление центра тяжести плоской ограниченной фигуры с помощью двойного интеграла. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal, Том-2, 64-71.
15. Усмонов, М.Т. (2021). Биномиальное распределение вероятностей. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal, Том-2, 81-85.
16. Усмонов, М.Т. (2021). Поток векторного поля. Поток через замкнутую поверхность. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal, Том-2, 52-63.
17. Усмонов, М.Т. (2021). Вычисление определенного интеграла по формуле трапеций и методом Симпсона. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal, Том-2, 213-225.
18. Усмонов, М.Т. (2021). Метод касательных. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal, Том-2, 25-34.

19. Усмонов,М.Т. (2021). Вычисление предела функции с помощью ряда. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal, Том-2, 92-96.
20. Усмонов,М.Т. (2021). Примеры решений произвольных тройных интегралов. Физические приложения тройного интеграла. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal, Том-2, 39-51.
21. Усмонов,М.Т. (2021). Вычисление двойного интеграла в полярной системе координат. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal, Том-2, 97-108.
22. Усмонов,М.Т. (2021). Криволинейный интеграл по замкнутому контуру. Формула Грина. Работа векторного поля. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal, Том-2, 72-80.
23. Усмонов,М.Т. (2021). Правило Крамера. Метод обратной матрицы. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal, Том-2, 249-255.
24. Усмонов,М.Т. (2021). Теоремы сложения и умножения вероятностей. Зависимые и независимые события. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal, Том-2, 202-212.
25. Усмонов,М.Т. (2021). Распределение и формула Пуассона. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal, Том-2, 86-91.

